

SmartCHP
COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

D.3.2

Report on the determination of the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

In this deliverable, the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO are determined. A combustion research unit system, which is mainly composed of a constant volume combustion chamber, is used to provide the well-controlled initial ambient conditions and fuel injection parameters. Based on the combustion chamber pressure trace, the heat release rate and mass fraction burned results are calculated with several careful corrections, and the indicators used to evaluate fuel ignition and combustion characteristics are defined. For engine application purposes, the effects of fuel upgrade (addition of alcohol or ignition improver) and various biomass origins (wood, sawmill residue, sunflower husks, and miscanthus) are investigated. The influences of initial chamber pressure and injection pressure are also studied. The results show that compared to ethanol, the addition of 30% of n-butanol could significantly improve the ignition and combustion processes of FPBO. However, the gain of Beraid addition is very limited. Higher initial chamber pressure boosts the fuel combustion reaction, while the change of injection pressure has marginal influence. Regarding the different biomass origins, FPBO from wood and miscanthus has higher chemical reactivity than that from sawmill residue and sunflower husks.

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Terminology

Abbreviation	Description
CHP	combined heat and power generation
CO	carbon monoxide
CP	combustion phasing
CRU	combustion research unit
CVCC	constant volume combustion chamber
EC	end of combustion
EHN	2-ethylhexyl nitrate
FPBO	fast pyrolysis bio-oil
HC	hydrocarbon
HFO	heavy-fuel oil
HRR	heat release rate
ID	ignition delay
NO_x	nitrogen oxides
PEG	polyethylene glycol
PM	particle matter
PRR	pressure rise rate
TDC	top dead center

1. Introduction

Using biomass-derived fuels to replace petroleum fuel is a promising way to fulfill carbon neutral combustion, curbing greenhouse gas emissions. Fast pyrolysis is an efficient process to convert biomass with lower energy densities to liquid biofuel with higher energy densities. In the process of fast pyrolysis, the organic materials are heated rapidly to 450 - 600 °C in the absence of oxygen, and after a short residence time of several seconds, the vapor is quickly condensed to a liquid called fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) [1, 2]. Typical feedstock includes forestry residues, agricultural byproducts such as rice straw, and organic waste such as paper waste.

FPBO is studied to fuel stationary diesel engines for combined heat and power generation (CHP). However, its special physical and chemical properties make the direct application in conventional diesel engines very constrained. Fuel properties of FPBO highly depend on the type of feedstock and the production process. Generally, FPBO has a high water content (15-30 wt.%), and a high oxygen content (30-50 wt.%) because it contains most of the oxygen in the original feedstock. Besides, it also contains some solid (tar, polymer, and char) and ash (metals and salts) particles.

When comparing the biofuel to commercial diesel fuel, ignition of FPBO in a compression ignition engine is delayed. This is a result caused by both the degraded atomization from the higher viscosity, and the lower chemical reactivity caused by the increased water content. The high acidity (pH 2-3) of FPBO may result in corrosion of the fuel supply and injection system. Its tendency to polymerize at elevated temperatures may lead to nozzle clogging and coking [1]. Given the poor physical properties and low propensity to autoignition, the use of FPBO in pure form in a diesel engine would be challenging. As a result, two feasible solutions exist: significant engine modification or upgrading of the fuel. Engine modifications, including installing pilot fuel injection system, elevating compression ratio and intake heating can improve FPBO ignition characteristics. Even so, it seems that fuel upgrade is still preferred according to current studies.

FPBO can be upgraded in a number of ways – physically, chemically and catalytically [3]. Compared with other upgrading methods, blending FPBO with a higher-quality base fuel shows superiority in the cost and convenience. Due to its polar properties, it is common practice in fuel blending to mix FPBO with polar solvents such as methanol, ethanol, or butanol [2, 4-9]. Blending FPBO with alcohol could effectively reduce the viscosity as well as the surface tension, increase its volatility, and prevent the polymerization, all of which improve the blend's stability and atomization characteristics. However, just like FPBO, the auto-ignition characteristics of alcohols are also much poorer than diesel. Therefore, researchers often add ignition improver into the fuel blends to meet the requirement of compression ignition in the unmodified diesel engine.

Lee *et al.* [5, 6] used a pilot injection of (bio-)diesel and a main injection of FPBO/ethanol blends with FPBO mass fraction up to 40%. Their results showed that stable engine operation was possible with this dual injection strategy, but the fuel conversion efficiency was slightly lower than that of diesel combustion. Despite the small penalty in efficiency, nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particle matter (PM) emissions were significantly decreased due to the high water- and oxygen content in the FPBO/ethanol blended fuel. Beld *et al.* [2] used a blend of 80 wt.% FPBO and 20 wt.% ethanol in a significantly modified four-cylinder stationary diesel engine genset. Stainless steel was used to produce all pumps, tubes and injection components which would be wetted by FPBO. They studied the effects of inlet temperature (from 90 to 220 °C) and injection timing (from -27 to -11 °CAD before TDC) on efficiency and emission. Results showed that an air inlet temperature of 150 °C was needed at their compression ratio of 18 to optimize their efficiency and emissions. Compared to diesel-fueled condition, carbon monoxide (CO) emissions were much higher, especially at air inlet temperatures below 100 °C. The overall efficiency (ratio of electricity output to fuel chemical energy input) fueled by the FPBO/ethanol blend is near to the diesel-fueled condition.

Ignition improvers such as 2-ethylhexyl nitrate (EHN) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) are typically used in FPBO/alcohol blends to for unmodified diesel engines. Lee *et al.* [7-9] used both two ignition improvers in FPBO/n-butanol blends with FPBO mass fractions of up to 30 wt.%. The proportion of ignition improver was chosen to match the different compression ratios, i.e. ignition improver of 40 wt.% (5 wt.% EHN + 35 wt.% PEG) for a compression ratio of 17:1 [7], ignition improver of 25% (5 wt.% EHN + 20 wt.% PEG) for 25:1 [9], and improver of 20% (5%EHN+15%PEG) for a compression ratio of 28:1 [8]. Results showed that the auto-ignition properties of FPBO/n-butanol blend were significantly enhanced by the excessive addition of ignition improvers. Compared to diesel fuel combustion, FPBO/n-butanol blends produced comparable (or less) hydrocarbon (HC) emissions and CO emissions but higher NO_x emissions. The PEG derivative ignition improver, Beraid, can be added to pure FPBO due to its polar property. It has been widely studied for improving ethanol combustion in compression ignition engine, but current studies show that the improvement of Beraid addition into FPBO is not satisfied [4].

Previous studies show that the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO are of great significance in both engine efficiency and pollutant emission. The ignition delay is regarded as the most important indicator for fuel ignition characteristics, whilst combustion phasing and combustion duration period are key indicators for fuel combustion characteristics. However, few studies reported an in-depth analysis on FPBO ignition and combustion process under diesel engine conditions, which is where the present work aims to contribute. In engine bench tests, the fuel ignition and combustion properties can be determined according to the in-cylinder pressure profile. However, the moving boundary and in-cylinder flow make it hard to observe the dependence of ignition propensity on independent boundary conditions such as ambient temperature and pressure. Therefore, the constant-volume combustion chamber (CVCC) has been widely used to determine the ignition and combustion characteristics of various fuels under diesel engine conditions [10-12]. Rabl *et al.* [10] used a commercially

available combustion research unit (CRU) made by Fueltech to analyze the relationship between the ignition delay and the combustion duration using two standard reference fuels. Emberger *et al.* [11] also used a CVCC device developed by Fueltech to test ignition and combustion characteristics of different vegetable oils and vegetable oil blends. In the authors' research group, Han *et al.* [12] previously studied ignition characteristics of ethanol/diesel and n-butanol/diesel blends using the CRU. These studies all showed that CRU and other similar CVCC devices could reach a well-controlled initial/boundary condition for the test of fuel ignition and combustion characteristics. Furthermore, the initial ambient pressure is provided by a high-pressure gas cylinder while the initial ambient temperature is adjusted by the electric heater, so different from engine bench tests, the ambient temperature and pressure in these CVCC devices are decoupled, which aids in identifying the effect of a single variable.

The objective of this work is to explore the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO. In Section 2, the experimental setup and test method are described. Section 3 is divided into four subsections according to the four types of tested fuels: pure FPBO, FPBO/alcohol blends, FPBO/Beraid blends, and FPBO from different biomass origins. Finally, the conclusion of this study is listed in Section 4.

2. SmartCHP system & components

2.1 Experimental setup

The combustion research unit (CRU) from Fueltech is used to measure the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO. Figure 2.1 shows a schematic of the constant volume combustion chamber (CVCC) in the CRU. The ambient gas is admitted to the chamber by an external high-pressure gas cylinder which contains the compressed synthetic air. And the chamber ambient pressure is measured by a static pressure sensor. Electric heaters are used to warm up the combustion chamber to the desired initial ambient temperature. Table 2.1 shows the basic specifications of CRU. Two thermocouples are installed at two different locations in the inner wall, measuring the chamber wall temperature. The differences between the two readings and the target wall temperature are both less than 1 °C, to minimize the non-uniformity of temperature field in the chamber.

Figure 2.1 Schematic overview of the CVCC system in the CRU

CRU is equipped with two sets of injection system: standard fuel injection system and heavy-fuel oil (HFO) injection system. Standard fuel injection system is used for testing fuels which have the similar viscosity as diesel. As shown in Figure 2.1

fuel sample from fuel reservoir is pressurized in the pressure amplifier where a ten-fold pressure amplification is achieved. A Bosch CRIP2 injector coupled with a 7-hole nozzle (part no. 0445110157, orifice diameter of 160 μm , umbrella angle of 158°) is mounted on the center of chamber top wall, equipped with a water-cooling system to avoid excessive temperature around the injector nozzle. Two dynamic pressure sensors (Kistler) are installed in the fuel rail and in the combustion chamber, respectively. The fuel pressure and chamber pressure are recorded at a rate of 50 kHz (intervals of 0.02 ms), from the start of injection to about 45 ms after that.

Table 2.1 CRU basic specifications

Parameter	Value
Chamber volume [L]	0.475
Chamber wall temperature [°C]	300 – 590
Initial chamber pressure [bar]	10 – 70
Injection pressure [bar]	300 – 1600 (200 – 1000 for HFO injector)
Injection duration [ms]	0 – 1.5

In HFO injection system, all the fuel reservoir, fuel pressurizer and injector are modified to achieve the fuel preheating (30 – 140 °C). Fuel preheating can significantly decrease the viscosity of heavy-fuel oil, which has ultra-low liquidity at room temperature. Besides, more modifications are implemented to facilitate the flushing and cleaning of the fuel supply system. The maximum fuel pressure in HFO injection system is limited to 1000 bar, and the 7-hole nozzle of HFO injector has the same parameters as the standard one.

2.2 Test method

Chamber pressure data are used to calculate heat release rate (HRR) and mass fraction burned (MFB) with the appropriate corrections. Based on these data, the indicators for evaluation of fuel ignition and combustion characteristics are defined at the end of this section.

2.2.1 Chamber pressure data and sound speed correction

Chamber pressure is monitored by the dynamic pressure sensor, which is installed underneath the injector nozzle tip with a distance, $d = 90 \text{ mm}$, as shown in Figure 2.1. The initial pressure wave is caused by local heat release in the autoignition point, and due to the limited propagation speed of pressure wave (i.e., speed of sound), there is a delay between start of ignition and pressure increase detected by dynamic pressure sensor. Therefore, the raw chamber pressure data needs to be corrected.

Figure 2.2 CVCC dimensions and sound speed correction

Applying sound speed correction requires two parameters: speed of sound and distance between pressure wave source and pressure sensor. The speed of sound under the ideal gas assumption can be calculated from the following equation,

$$v_s = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma RT}{M}} \quad (2.1)$$

where γ is the specific heat ratio of chamber ambient gas, R is the universal gas constant, T is the ambient temperature, and M is the mean molecular weight of chamber ambient gas ($M = 0.02895 \text{ kg/mol}$ for air). For all test conditions, air is used as ambient gas, the initial wall temperature is assumed to be the same as the ambient temperature, T , and the specific heat ratio of air, γ , is determined from the γ - T table [13] of air by linear interpolation between the two closest temperature. The exact location of pressure wave source varies with the different fuels and different ambient conditions, but generally, the initial autoignition point appears in the downstream of spray axis. In the present study, the distance between pressure sensor and spray axis, h , is used as the propagation distance of sound. As shown in the Figure 2.2, $h = d \cos 11^\circ$, where $d = 90 \text{ mm}$.

The sound speed and propagation distance are used to evaluate the pressure signal delay, $t_d = h/v_s$. Then, t_d is used to correct the recorded pressure-time paired data. For a typical test condition at 590° , the pressure signal delay is 0.153 ms .

2.2.2 Heat release rate (HRR) and heat transfer correction

Chamber pressure data can be used to calculate the gross heat release rate (HRR) from fuel combustion reaction. According to energy conservation, in CVCC system, the gross heat-release rate, i.e., chemical energy release rate, dQ_{ch}/dt , can be determined with the following equation,

$$\frac{dQ_{ch}}{dt} = \frac{dQ_n}{dt} + \frac{dQ_{ht}}{dt} \quad (2.2)$$
 where dQ_n/dt is the net heat release rate and dQ_{ht}/dt is the rate of heat transfer to the chamber wall. Because the sensible enthalpy of injected fuel is little, it is neglected in the energy conservation equation. The net heat release rate in CVCC is derived with the equation,

$$\frac{dQ_n}{dt} = \frac{1}{\gamma-1} V \frac{dp}{dt} \quad (2.3)$$

where γ is the specific heat ratio of chamber ambient gas, V is the total volume of chamber, and dp/dt is the pressure rise rate (PRR).

In Figure 2.3, the blue curves show the chamber pressure (top) and PRR (bottom) profiles. The sound speed correction has been applied. For the high activity fuels like diesel, the chemical energy can be released in a short period, generating a steep pressure increase. The mean temperature of ambient gas also rises, while the temperature of chamber wall keeps almost unchanged because of thermal inertia. Hence, there is a heat loss due to the heat transfer from ambient gas to chamber wall, which makes the pressure profile turns to drop after it reaches the peak. From Equation (2.2), after the combustion reaction is finished, $\frac{dQ_{ch}}{dt} = 0$, so that $\frac{dQ_{ht}}{dt} = -\frac{dQ_n}{dt}$. In this study, a simple heat transfer model is used to evaluate the heat transfer rate from ambient gas to chamber wall. We assume the thermodynamic state inside the chamber is uniform. The mean temperature of ambient gas T_{mean} , is a function of the chamber pressure under ideal gas assumption. According to the Fourier's law, heat transfer rate can be determined with the following equation,

$$Q_{ht} = -kA(T_{mean} - T_{initial}) \quad (2.4)$$

where A is the total area of chamber inner surface, k is a constant, and $T_{initial}$ is the setting temperature for each case. kA can be determined using the PRR data after the combustion reaction is finished,

$$kA = -\frac{V}{(\gamma-1)(T_{mean}-T_{initial})} \frac{dp}{dt} \quad (2.5)$$

It is worth noting that the low reactivity fuels are likely to finish combustion reaction beyond CRU recording period (45 ms), which means that kA cannot be determined from case to case. Therefore, the kA calculated from the benchmark condition (as shown in Figure 2.3) is applied to all the test cases for heat transfer rate calculation.

Figure 2.3 Top: raw chamber pressure and corrected accumulated heat release profiles. Bottom: raw PRR and corrected HRR profiles. The detailed test condition is shown in the figure.

The orange curves in Figure 2.3. are the accumulated heat release (top) and HRR (bottom) profiles. The accumulated heat release is the integration of dQ_{ch}/dt (i.e., HRR), which levels off after it reaches the peak, meaning that the heat transfer model is validated. The accumulated heat release is not a strict horizontal line after the combustion reaction is finished. This is because that in the actual situation, the heat transfer from ambient gas to chamber wall is complicated: on one hand, the temperature fields of both ambient gas and chamber wall non-uniform; on the other hand, during combustion process, spray flame/wall interaction is probably to happen due to the small chamber diameter, which makes the heat transfer difficult to model. Current model is adequate for HRR calculation, more detailed improvement is beyond the topic of the present study.

2.2.3 Mass fraction burned (MFB)

Mass fraction burned (MFB) is a function of time to present the proportion of released heat in the chemical energy of the injected fuel. For instance, 10% MFB means at certain moment, 10% of the fuel chemical energy is released through combustion reaction. MFB is calculated from the integration of HRR divided by the total chemical energy of the injected fuel. The direct connection between injection

volume and injection parameters is unknown, so that the indirect method is applied to evaluate the injection volume. From the benchmark case using EN590 diesel (as shown in Figure 2.3), the injection volume (V_{inj}), can be calculated from the maximum of accumulated heat release ($Q_{ch,max}$) with $V_{inj} = Q_{ch,max}/LHV$, where LHV is the volumetric lower heating value of diesel. As shown in Figure 2.4, the negative integration of HRR at the beginning is caused by the fuel evaporation cooling effect, and hence the latent heat of evaporation is considered when correcting the integration of HRR includes. In this study, the injection duration is fixed at 1.5 ms, so that the injection volume at each injection pressure is benchmarked using diesel. For example, the calculated injection volume at injection pressure of 1500 bar is 0.079 ml. And it is assumed that the injection volume at the same injection pressure keeps constant for different fuels. It is worth noting that injection volume is also slightly influenced by the physical properties of fuel, like viscosity and volatility, while in this study these effects are neglected.

Figure 2.4 Left: correction of the integration of HRR. Right: MFB profile for the benchmark case.

When calculating MFB for each case, the volumetric LHV of the tested fuel sample is first determined based on the components of fuel blends. Then, the chemical energy of the injected fuel equals to the volumetric LHV multiplied by the tabulated injection volume. Finally, MFB is calculated from the corrected integration of HRR divided by the chemical energy of the injected fuel, as shown in the right subplot of Figure 2.4.

2.2.4 Definitions of indicators

Table 2.2 shows the definitions of indicators for evaluating the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO and its blends. In some other studies, a small amount of pressure increase, such as 0.2 bar, is used to define ignition delay [14]. However, the fixed pressure increase is not reasonable for evaluating ignition characteristics when using different injection volume or different fuels. In this

study, the moment for 5% MFB is used to define the ignition delay (ID). This definition is more instructional for combustion control in real engine and has been widely used in CVCC experiments [15, 16].

For the definition of the end of combustion (EC), many studies define it as the moment for 85%–95% MFB [15, 16]. However, as mentioned before, FPBO is condensed from the pyrolysis vapor at 450 - 600 °C, so that FPBO has some heavy components which is difficult to evaporate. The combustion duration of FPBO is much longer than that of diesel, and hence, in this study, we reduce the criterion for the EC definition to 80% MFB, i.e., the moment when 80% of injected fuel energy is released. Combustion duration period is used to evaluate the time needed for consumption of most of fuel and it is defined as the period between ID and EC.

Table 2.2 Definitions of indicators

Indicator	Unit	Explanation
Ignition delay, ID	[ms]	Moment for 5%MFB
Combustion phasing, CP	[ms]	Moment for maximum HRR
End of combustion, EC	[ms]	Moment for 80%MFB
Combustion acceleration period	[ms]	Period between ID and CP (CP-ID)
Combustion duration period	[ms]	Period between ID and EC (EC-ID)

Combustion phasing (CP) plays an important role in engine efficiency and has obtained much attention in engine combustion research. In many studies, CP is defined as the moment when 50% of injection fuel energy is released [17]. However, considering that FPBO combustion efficiency is relatively low in some test conditions, in this study, CP is defined as the moment for maximum heat release rate. This definition is also adopted in IP541 standard for evaluation the combustion characteristics of heavy fuel oil [18]. For FPBO at lower chamber wall temperature or lower initial chamber pressure, both ID and CP are quite long. To better understand the combustion characteristics of such fuel, the combustion acceleration period, which is defined as the period between ID and CP, is used to evaluate the developing speed of the combustion progress.

In CRU experiments, the results of HRR, MFB and indicators are averaged from 5 repetitive tests in each test condition. Figure 2.5 shows an example of the results. The fuel blend tested is 90%FPBO+10%n-butanol (by mass). The solid red line is the averaged data from 5 repetitive tests, whilst the red shadow area shows the 95% confidence interval of the averaged data. The dashed lines are from 5 individual tests. ID, CP, EC, combustion acceleration period, and combustion duration period are presented in the figure.

Figure 2.5 An example of heat release rate (HRR), mass fraction burned (MFB) profiles and indicators. Test condition: fuel of 90%FPBO+10%n-butanol, chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, initial chamber pressure of 70 bar, injection pressure of 400 bar.

2.3 Tested fuels and conditions

In this study, FPBO and its blends (FPBO/ethanol, FPBO/n-butanol, FPBO/Beraid) are studied. Besides, the effects of initial chamber pressure and injection pressure are also performed. Table 2.3 shows the tested conditions. Previous engine studies revealed that a higher in-cylinder temperature at top dead center (TDC) was required to keep stable operation when fueled with FPBO, and hence the engine modifications were generally employed, such as intake air preheating and elevated compression ratio [2, 4]. The chamber wall temperature investigated in this study is fixed at 590 °C. Initial test also reveals that a slight drop in chamber wall temperature leads to obvious worsening of the combustion process. Fuel preheating to 50 °C is used to increase the fluidity of FPBO due to its high viscosity at room temperature. It is worth noting that FPBO has the tendency to polymerize at elevated temperature, so that the recommend fuel preheating temperature is limited to 60 °C.

Table 2.3 Test conditions in CRU

Parameter	Value
Chamber wall temperature [°C]	590
Initial chamber pressure [bar]	30 – 70
Injection pressure [bar]	400 – 1000
Injection duration [ms]	1.5
Fuel preheating temperature [°C]	50

Table 2.4 Fuel properties of diesel, FPBO, n-butanol, and ethanol

Property	Unit	Diesel	FPBO ^(a)	n-Butanol	Ethanol
LHV	MJ/kg	42.6	16.4	33.1	28.9
	MJ/L	34.9	19.2	26.8	22.5
Density	kg/L	0.82	1.17	0.81	0.78
C	mass %	85.0	42.8	64.8	52.2
H	mass %	12.6	7.8	13.6	13.0
O	mass %	-	49.2	21.6	34.8
Water	mass %	-	24.1	-	-
Solid	mass %	-	0.04	-	-
Viscosity (40 °C)	cSt	2.7	21	3.1	1.1
pH	-	-	2.6	-	-
Cetane number	-	54.8	-	17	8

(a) Properties of FPBO are based on Ref. [2]

Table 2.4 shows the properties of diesel, FPBO, n-butanol and ethanol. Besides these fuels, an ignition improver, Beraid (poly-ethylene-glycol derivative from Akzo Nobel), is also used to enhance the chemical reactivity with FPBO. However, to the best of authors' knowledge, the details of its properties are not available.

3. Results and discussion

This section reports the ignition and combustion characteristics of pure FPBO, FPBO/alcohol, FPBO/Beraid, and FPBO from different biomass origins. In each subsection, the tested fuel blends are first introduced and then the HRR, MFB, and indicators of each test cases are presented and discussed.

3.1 Pure FPBO

Figure 3.1 HRR and MFB profiles for pure wood-based FPBO combustion at different initial chamber pressure, 30 bar and 50 bar, respectively. Test condition: chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, injection pressure of 1000 bar.

Wood-based FPBO is tested in CRU as the reference. Figure 3.1 shows the HRR and MFB profiles for pure FPBO at two different initial chamber pressure, 30 and 50 bar. At initial chamber pressure of 50 bar, HRR profile reaches the peak value at around 5 ms, and then drops to a low level after 10 ms until the end of CRU recording (45ms). The fuel conversion rate is lower than 30% at 10 ms, which means that most of FPBO experiences a relatively slow oxidization process rather than releases the chemical energy through the intense combustion reaction process. This is because: 1) the poor fuel atomization process results from the large viscosity and the high molecular weight species due to polymerization whose boiling point is very high; 2) the proportion of high-reactivity contents is relatively low which cannot provide sufficient local temperature rise to trigger the chain reaction of the low-reactivity content. Therefore, fueling FPBO in diesel engine generally requires engine modification to reach a much higher in-cylinder

temperature at TDC, such as intake preheating and elevated compression ratio. The higher temperature is beneficial to improving both physical evaporation process and chemical reaction process.

3.2 FPBO with addition of alcohol

Previous studies show that blending FPBO with alcohol can improve the fuel stability in long term storage, inhibit the polymerization tendency, and reduce the viscosity. Ethanol and n-butanol are widely used to blend with FPBO. In this study, two FPBO/alcohol blends, i.e., 70%FPBO+30%Ethanol and 70%FPBO+30% Butanol (all by mass fraction), are investigated in CRU.

Figure 3.2 HRR and MFB profiles for pure FPBO, 70%FPBO+30%Ethanol, and 70%FPBO+30%Butanol. Test condition: chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, initial chamber pressure of 50 bar, injection pressure of 1000 bar.

Figure 3.2 compares HRR and MFB profiles of pure FPBO, 70%FPBO+30%Ethanol and 70%FPBO+30%Butanol. It is shown that the chemical reactivity of ethanol is lower than that of FPBO. For 70%FPBO+30%Ethanol, even though the viscosity is reduced, there is only a small peak in HRR profile at around 5 ms, and most of the fuel is oxidized with a relatively low speed and a low fuel conversion rate. Differ from ethanol, the addition of 30% n-butanol could significantly improve the ignition and combustion performance: the peak value of HRR is elevated and advanced, and the fuel conversion rate could reach higher than 90% within 15 ms. Hence, for CRU test conditions, addition of n-butanol is an effective way to

upgrade FPBO. In the rest of this section, 70%FPBO+30%Butanol is used as reference fuel to investigate the effects of initial chamber pressure and injection pressure.

Figure 3.3 HRR and MFB profiles for different initial chamber pressure. Test condition: fuel of 70%FPBO+30% Butanol, chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, injection pressure of 1000 bar.

Figure 3.4 ID, CP, EC, combustion acceleration period (CP-ID), and combustion duration period (EC-ID) as a function of initial chamber pressure. Test condition: the same with Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 shows the HRR and MFB profiles at different initial chamber pressure, and Figure 3.4 presents the effects of initial chamber pressure on the indicators of fuel ignition and combustion characteristics. It is clear to see that the increase of initial chamber pressure could obviously elevate the HRR peak and promote the fuel conversion rate. 70%FPBO+30%Butanol presents a low reaction rate at 30 bar: ID is longer than 7 ms, CP is delayed to around 30 ms. However, when the initial chamber pressure rises to 50 bar, all ID, CP and EC decrease, the combustion acceleration period (CP-ID) is shortened to around 1 ms and the combustion duration period is about 6 ms. After the initial chamber pressure further increases to 70 bar, ID and CP change slightly, while EC is advanced to around 4.5 ms. In this study, the chamber wall temperature is fixed at 590 °C, so that the increase of initial chamber pressure means the higher oxygen concentration, i.e., more sufficient oxygen supply. Besides, higher pressure leads to higher charge density, which leads to the better atomization process of fuel spray. For the real engine application, it is indicated that besides temperature, the pressure at TDC also plays an important role in FPBO combustion. The higher pressure, which can be achieved by intake boost or elevated compression ratio,

could shorten the combustion duration period of FPBO and improve the combustion efficiency.

Figure 3.5 HRR and MFB profiles for different injection pressure. Test condition: fuel of 70%FPBO+30% Butanol, chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, initial chamber pressure of 50 bar.

Figure 3.6 ID, CP, EC, combustion acceleration period (CP-ID), and combustion duration period (EC-ID) as a function of injection pressure. Test condition: the same with Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6 show the effects of injection pressure on the ignition and combustion process of 70%FPBO+30%Butanol. At the same injection duration period, the higher injection pressure generally leads to the larger injection volume. When the injection pressure rises from 400 bar to 800 bar, caused by the increased injection volume, the evaporation cooling effect following the start of injection becomes more significant, while the indicators such as ID, CP and EC keep almost unchanged. After the injection pressure further increases to 1000 bar, the larger amount of injected fuel causes a slight delay of ID as well as EC. Overall, it is indicated that the effects of injection pressure on the fuel ignition and combustion characteristics are inapparent.

The previous studies on diesel fuel injection showed that at lower injection pressure, the elevated injection pressure can improve the atomization process and hence contribute to the shorter ID, while the effects of injection pressure on ID becomes negligible at higher range of injection pressure. In BTG's engine bench test, an in-line pump was employed to provide an injection pressure of 200 – 300 bar [2, 4]. In real engine, the fuel injection volume per cycle is determined from the engine load and speed. Increasing fuel injection pressure can reduce the injection duration, leading to a shorter combustion duration which helps improves engine efficiency. But meanwhile, elevated injection pressure also creates much challenge for fuel injection system design, and accordingly results in the increased engine cost.

3.3 FPBO with addition of ignition improver

Addition of ignition improver is a common way to improve the fuel ignitability in compression ignition engines. Generally, ignition improvers have high chemical reactivity, and during the low-temperature reaction phase, they can produce many chemical radicals as well as a relatively large amount of heat, which can boost the combustion reaction of low reactivity components in the fuel. In this study, the ignition improver, Beraid, is added into FPBO. Beraid is polar liquid and can be soluble with water and lower alcohols. It has been widely used to improve the autoignition of methanol and ethanol in compression ignition engine.

Figure 3.7 HRR and MFB profiles for different ignition improver content at various initial chamber pressure. Test condition: chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, injection pressure of 1000 bar.

Figure 3.8 ID, CP, and combustion acceleration period (CP-ID) as a function of ignition improver mass fraction. Test condition: chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, initial chamber pressure of 50 bar, injection pressure of 1000 bar.

Figure 3.7 shows the HRR and MFB profiles of pure FPBO, 92%FPBO+8%Beraid and 88%FPBO+ 12%Beraid, the effects of initial chamber pressure also included. Figure 3.8 presents the indicators as a function of Beraid mass fraction at initial chamber pressure of 50 bar. At 50 bar, adding 8% Beraid into FPBO could increase the initial heat release rate to some extent, and slightly improve the fuel conversion rate. Further increasing Beraid content to 12% just leads to the very limited improvement. It is indicated that the gain of adding Beraid into FPBO is not satisfied, and the increase of Beraid content cannot further boost the autoignition process. The similar results were also report in some studies [4]. This is mainly because Beraid was initially designed for applying ethanol in

compression ignition engines. Besides the higher chemical reactivity, Beraid also has a high viscosity which can improve the lubricity of ethanol fuel. When adding Beraid to FPBO, the mixed fuel has a high viscosity, leading to the poor atomization process, so the improvement of Beraid addition is limited. As shown in Figure 3.8, compared with pure FPBO, the addition of 8% Beraid just reduce the ID and CP by around 1 ms, and the combustion acceleration period keeps almost constant.

From the above discussion, it can be inferred that improving the atomization process by reducing viscosity is as important as increasing the proportion of high-reactivity components in upgrade of FPBO for engine application. For example, the addition of 30% ethanol significantly reduces viscosity, but due to the low chemical reactivity of ethanol, the ignition property of 70%FPBO+30%Ethanol is still poor. On the other hand, the addition of 8% Beraid increases the proportion of high-reactivity components, but the improvements in ignition and combustion properties are not satisfied due to the poor atomization process. It seems that the ternary mixture of FPBO, alcohol and ignition improver could be a potential solution for FPBO upgrade. Furthermore, some commercial ignition improvers which are designed for conventional fuel, such as 2-ethylhexyl nitrate and di-tert-butyl peroxide, are immiscible with FPBO, but probably alcohols can work as the co-solvent to form the uniform and stable fuel mixture.

3.4 FPBO from different biomass origins

Different FPBO samples made from different biomass origins are also studied. Table 3.1 shows the nomenclatures for the FPBO samples from 4 different biomass origins: wood, sawmill residue, sunflower husks, and miscanthus. As mentioned in Section 3.2, blending FPBO with 30% n-butanol could improve both the atomization process and the combustion process, and it seems that this is the best way to upgrade FPBO to fit for CRU operation condition compared to blending with ethanol or adding Beraid. Therefore, these 4 FPBO samples are blended with 30% n-butanol and tested in CRU.

Table 3.1 Nomenclature for FPBO from different biomass origins

FPBO nomenclature	Biomass origin
FPBO	Wood
FPBOb	Sawmill residue
FPBOc	Sunflower husks
FPBOd	Miscanthus

Figure 3.9 and Figure 3.10 show the HRR and MFB profiles of these 4 FPBO/n-butanol blends at initial chamber pressure of 50 bar and 70 bar, respectively. FPBO samples from 4 biomass origins have the big differences in the ignition and combustion characteristics. At 50 bar, FPBO (wood) and FPBOd (miscanthus) have the similar HRR profiles and their chemical reactivities are much higher than

the other 2 samples, FPBOb and FPBOc, which experience a slow combustion process. The reactivity of FPBOb is slightly higher than that of FPBOc at 50 bar, while with the initial chamber pressure increasing to 70 bar, FPBOb could release most of chemical energy within 20 ms but FPBOc still experiences a long oxidization process. The following chemical reactivity relationship among 4 FPBO samples is inferred: $FPBO \approx FPBOd \gg FPBOb > FPBOc$.

Figure 3.9 HRR and MFB profiles for FPBO from different biomass origins blended with 30% n-butanol. Test condition: chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, initial chamber pressure of 50 bar, injection pressure of 1000 bar.

Figure 3.10 HRR and MFB profiles for FPBO from different biomass origins blended with 30% n-butanol. Test condition: chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, initial chamber pressure of 70 bar, injection pressure of 1000 bar.

In addition, the differences in LHV among 4 FPBO samples are also indicated from MFB profiles. The LHV of FPBO is from Reference [2] and applied to MFB calculation of all FPBO samples. However, as shown in Figure 3.9 and Figure 3.10, the largest MFB of FPBOd is around 130%. It is indicated that the LHV of FPBOd (miscanthus) is much higher than wood-based FPBO. The following LHV relationship among 4 FPBO samples is inferred: $FPBOd \gg FPBO \approx FPBOb \approx FPBOc$.

The differences in combustion characteristics and LHV are caused by the differences in components of FPBO. FPBO generally has a water content of 15% – 30%. Water content plays a crucial role in both combustion characteristics and LHV. The higher water content worsens the ignition and combustion process and lowers the LHV. Hence, the dried feedback or the biomass with lower water content could lead to a higher heating value and reactivity. Besides, the

proportion of other components of FPBO is also dependent from the biomass origins. As reported in Ref. [19], FPBO can be divided into water-soluble and water-insoluble fractions. The former consists mainly of water, “sugars” (sugar type compounds, ether-insolubles), acids, aldehydes, ketones, pyrans and furans, while the later consist mainly of lignin material, extractives (neutral substances) and solids. The detailed components of incomplete pyrolysis products like sugars and lignin are highly dependent on the biomass origins. In the design of real engine, the variation in FPBO property from different biomass origins should be fully considered. Usually, by elevating compression ratio and using intake preheating, the increase of temperature at TDC makes the difference in fuel ignition and combustion characteristics less obvious. However, for FPBO products with high water content and low reactivity, the proper fuel upgrade like addition of n-butanol and ignition improver is still in need.

Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil (Pine)		wet	dry	C	H	N	O	pKa
Whole oil		23,9	0	53,3	6,5	0,08	40	
Water	wt-%	23,9	0					15,7
Acids	wt-%	4,3	5,6	40,0	6,7	0	53,3	3 - 5
Formic acid	wt-%		1,5					3,8
Acetic acid	wt-%		3,4					4,7
Propionic acid	wt-%		0,2					
Glycolic acid	wt-%		0,6					3,8
Alcohols	wt-%	2,2	2,9	37,5	12,5	0	50,0	15 - 16
Ethylene glycol	wt-%		0,3					15
Methanol	wt-%		2,6					16
Aldehydes, ketones, furans, pyrans	wt-%	15,4	20,3					16 - 36
Nonaromatic Aldehydes	wt-%		9,72	40,0	6,7	0,0	53,3	17
Aromatic Aldehydes	wt-%		0,009					17
Nonaromatic Ketones	wt-%		5,36	48,6	8,11	0,0	43,2	20
Furans	wt-%		3,37					32 - 36
Pyrans	wt-%		1,10					32 - 34
Sugars	wt-%	34,4	45,3	44,1	6,6	0,1	49,2	3 - 16
Anhydro-β-D-arabino-furanose, 1,5-	wt-%		0,27					
Anhydro-β-D-glucopyranose(Levogluconan)	wt-%		4,01					
Dianhydro-α-D-glucopyranose, 1,4:3,6-	wt-%		0,17					
Hydroxy, sugar acids	wt-%							3 - 5
LMM lignin	wt-%	13,4	17,7	68	6,7	0,1	25,2	9 - 10
Catechols	wt-%		0,06					
Lignin derived Phenols	wt-%		0,09					10
Guaiacols (Methoxy phenols)	wt-%		3,82					10
HMM lignin	wt-%	1,95	2,6	63,5	5,9	0,3	30,3	
Extractives	wt-%	4,35	5,7	75,4	9,0	0,2	15,4	7 - 16
Fatty acids	wt-%							9-10
Triglycerides	wt-%							
Resin acids	wt-%							7

Figure 3.11 Composition of FPBO from pine [19]

4. Conclusion

In this study, a combustion research unit equipped with a heavy-fuel oil injection system is used to evaluate the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO. The wood-based FPBO is first tested as a reference. Then, for engine application purposes, FPBO/alcohol and FPBO/Beraid blends are investigated. Finally, FPBO samples made from other three biomass origins, sawmill residue, sunflower husks and miscanthus, are also studied. The wall temperature of CRU chamber is fixed at 590 °C. The effects of initial chamber pressure (30 – 70 bar) and injection pressure (400 – 1000 bar) on FPBO blends are studied. The main findings from this study can be concluded as follows.

- The chemical reactivity of FPBO is much lower than diesel-like fuel. At chamber pressure of 50 bar, the injected FPBO releases around 30% of chemical energy during the initial low-temperature reaction phase, which is followed by a relatively long and gentle oxidization process.
- FPBO with addition of 30% of ethanol leads to a worse ignition property because the chemical reactivity of ethanol is lower than that of FPBO, even though the reduced viscosity of blended fuel could improve the atomization process.
- FPBO with addition of 30% of n-butanol results in an improved ignition and combustion property. The increase of initial chamber pressure is beneficial to improve the ignition and combustion process, leading to the advanced ignition delay, shortened combustion duration and elevated fuel conversion rate. But the change of injection pressure plays a marginal role in the combustion process of FPBO/n-butanol blends.
- FPBO with addition of 8% of ignition improver, Beraid, could obviously boost the heat release rate during the low-temperature reaction phase, while the whole combustion process is not significantly improved due to the limited amount of high reactivity components. The gain is not obvious when further increasing the proportion of Beraid to 12%.
- The origin of biomass has huge influence on the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO products. FPBO from wood and miscanthus has higher chemical reactivity than that from sawmill residue and sunflower husks.

5. References

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